

I-Vision: Smart Equipment for Assisting Blind or Visually Impaired People

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Abstract.

Blind and visually impaired suffer in their lives in many different things, such as recognizing the things in front of them, reading texts, and many other things. Therefore, using the technology which related to deal with images, analyzing them, and knowing what is in them, as the human mind does, because everything in front of it is images that analyze these images in a very short time and know what is in them in all the details. This technology is Computer Vision, as it is the best technology in dealing with images and analyzing them. This paper proposes I-Vision which is an equipment that consists of a mini-camera and mini-computer, which work in conjunction with the mobile application to provide a user-friendly experience for the visually impaired to assist the blind and visually impaired people to detect the objects, recognize faces, read text, recognize food, describe the scenes around them and finally recognize the Egyptian money. So, I-Vision, can helps the blind and visually impaired in many matters in their daily lives.

Key Words: Computer vision, visually impaired, Blind Assistance System, Smart Glasses.

1-Introduction

World Health Organization has the number of visually impaired people globally, based on the latest studies, that there are about 285 million people who suffer from visual impairment worldwide, of whom 246 million are visually impaired and 39 One million people are blind. It also estimated that the Eastern Mediterranean region constitutes 12.6% of the blindness rate in the world In Egypt, the number of blind people in Egypt is estimated at about 3.5 million Egyptian blind people, and the number of blind people enrolled in different stages of education is about 37 thousand blind people. [1]

Visually impaired and blind people find it difficult to face their day-to-day problems because of their impairment. Computer vision technology has the potential to revolutionize the lives of blind people by providing them with greater independence, safety, and access to information.

Computer vision is a field of artificial intelligence that focuses on enabling machines to interpret and understand visual data from the world around them. It involves the use of algorithms and mathematical models to analyze, process, and interpret images and videos captured by cameras or other sensors. Computer vision has a wide range of applications, including object recognition, facial recognition, autonomous vehicles, medical imaging, and surveillance systems. So, with the rapid advancement of technology in recent years,

computer vision has become an increasingly important area of research and development with significant potential for improving many aspects of our daily lives. [2]

This paper represents the proposed system which is composed of a mini-camera and mini-computer, which work in conjunction with the mobile application to provide a user-friendly experience for the visually impaired. The proposed system offers a comprehensive and integrated solution that aims to improve the quality of life for blind and visually impaired individuals by reducing their reliance on other people.

The remaining part of this paper is organized as follows: section 2 provides a survey over some existing apps in the Google play market and the AppStore. Section 3 displays the methodology; section 4 shows the main algorithm and implementation details. Section 5 summarized the results and the possible enhancements, while section 5 concludes the paper.

2-Related Work

There are several mobile applications on multiple platforms such as Android, IOS and windows, which were developed with the visually impaired and blind people to assist them. These applications can be divided into different categories like object detection, reading text, cash recognition, face recognition, and describing scene.

Related works are divided into related mobile applications and related products.

2.1- Related Mobile Applications

SuperSense is an application on Android Google Play store and IOS Apple store, this application assists visually impaired and blind people of all ages using AI (Artificial Intelligence). This app is useful for reading text on post, packaging, signs, documents, etc. and read any text format, identifies currency, enhanced Bar code reader to identify products, guides you on how to point your camera during use, smart scanner automatically detects. [3]

Lookout is an application on Android Google Play store and IOS Apple store, it uses computer vision to assist people with low vision or blindness get things done faster and more easily. Using your phone's camera, Lookout makes it easier to get more information about the world around you and do daily tasks more efficiently like sorting mail, putting away groceries, and more it helps blind and visually impaired people learn about their surroundings. [4]

2.2- Related Products

OrCam MyEye is a wearable assistive technology device designed to help people with visual impairments or reading difficulties. It is a small, lightweight device that attaches to the user's eyeglasses or sunglasses and uses artificial intelligence (AI) to read text, recognize faces, and identify objects. The device consists of a small camera that captures images of the user's surroundings and sends them to a computer processor that analyzes the images in real-time. The device then provides audio feedback to the user through a small speaker or headphones. [5]

Aira is a technology company that helps people who are blind or visually impaired. The company uses a combination of wearable technology, artificial intelligence, and human agents to provide real-time visual information to users. Aira's main product is a pair of smart glasses that are equipped with a camera and other sensors. When a user needs assistance, they can connect with an Aira agent who can see what the user sees through the camera on the glasses. The agent can then provide verbal guidance and assistance to help the user. [6]

Envision is an artificial intelligence product that helps visually impaired individuals to navigate their surroundings and perform daily tasks with ease. The app uses advanced computer vision and machine learning algorithms to recognize and describe objects, text, and people in real-time. Envision can read out loud any text that the user points their product's camera at, including books, signs, menus, and labels. It can also identify colors, currencies, and even emotions on people's faces. The app has a voice assistant that guides users through the different features and provides feedback on their actions. [7]

Table 1: Competitive Analysis

Competitor Features	I-Vision	SuperSense	Lookout	OrCam MyEye	Aria	Envision
Object Detection	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓
Reading Text	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Describe Scene	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓
Cash Recognition	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓
Face Recognition	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓
Food Recognition	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗

Table 1 illustrates the comparative analysis that compare the I-Vision product features with the other applications features from the table we can see that I-Vision product covers all the features and provides an additional feature which is food recognition.

3- Research Methodology

The methodology for developing a blind assistance system typically involves several steps, including identifying the requirements of the system, designing the system architecture, selecting appropriate algorithms, implementing the system, testing, and evaluating its performance, and finally, refining and improving the system based on tests.

Our methodology is divided into software, hardware, mobile application, and the integration between them as shown in Figure 1. Each feature was developed by building appropriate models for it, testing it, and collecting the appropriate data for it to increase the accuracy of each model for a specific feature. Also, develop a mobile application which consider as a control device for the smart equipment, the hardware part is a small computer and a camera on which the model for each feature is run, and finally the integration part between the small computer and the mobile was made. The following parts explain the features and the algorithms, and the techniques used for implementing them.

Figure 1: System Methodology

3.1-Feature 1: Object Detection with COCO Dataset.

Object detection is a computer vision technique that allows us to identify and locate objects in an image or video. With this kind of identification and localization, object detection can be used to count objects in a scene and determine and track their precise locations, all while accurately labeling them and recognize the object with bounding box in the image, so we can say that object detection is divided into two things (classification and localization) but in multiple objects as shown in figure 2. [8]

Computer Vision Tasks

Figure 2: Computer Vision Tasks

SSD (Model Architecture): SSD is abbreviation of single shot detector and it's divided into three main things.

Single Shot: this means that the tasks of object localization and classification are done in a single forward pass of the network.

Multi Box: this is the name of a technique for bounding box regression.

Detectors: are convolutional filters, Each detector outputs a single value. discretizes the output space of bounding boxes into a set of default boxes over different aspect ratios and scales per feature map location. At prediction time, the network generates scores for the presence of each object category in each default box and produces adjustments to the box to better match the object shape. Additionally, the network combines predictions from multiple feature maps with different resolutions to naturally handle objects of various sizes. Our SSD model is simple relative to methods that require object proposals because it eliminates proposal generation and subsequent pixel or feature resampling stage and encapsulates all computation in a single network. This makes SSD easy to train and straightforward to integrate into systems that require a detection component, as represented in figure 3. [9]

Figure 3: MobileNet & SSD

COCO Dataset: COCO stands for Common Objects in Context, as the image dataset was created with the goal of advancing image recognition. The COCO dataset contains challenging, high-quality visual datasets for computer vision, mostly state-of-the-art neural networks, it contains over 200'000 images of the total 330'000 images are labeled, 1.5 Mio object instances and 80 object categories (person, car, chair, etc.)

Based on the that the number of classes is limited, and it is only 80 classes, and in our world, there are many classes unlimited, which leads to the that there may be an error in identifying a specific object, and this object does not exist in these classes and our goal is to provide as many classes as possible to help the blind more, so we suggest using an API called google vision this API Provides general label and bounding box annotations for multiple objects recognized in a single image. [10]

3.2-Feature 2: Text reader with OCR.

Text recognition stage transforms text pictures into a string of characters or sentences. Words are an elementary entity used by humans for visual recognition, hence converting images of text into words is critical.

Character recognition and word recognition are two different techniques of recognition. Character recognition algorithms separate a text image into several single-character cutouts.

For these strategies, character separation between adjacent characters is crucial, it is using the Optical Character Recognition module (OCR) is used in the recognition process, where images are first segmented into k classes, followed by binary text image hypothesis generation, which passes through connected components analysis and the greyscale consistency constraint module before being fed to OCR, In Computer Vision the method of converting the text present in images or scanned documents to a machine-readable format that can later be edited, searched, and can be used for further processing is known as Optical Character Recognition (OCR). Word recognition recognizes words from text images by combining character recognition outputs with language models or lexicons. In the case of degraded characters, it can be employed. Word recognition is a superior approach to character recognition for situations with a restricted number of word possibilities in input photos.

Tesseract OCR: Tesseract is an open-source text recognition (OCR) Engine, available under the Apache 2.0 license. It can be used directly, or (for programmers) using an API to extract printed text from images. It supports a wide variety of languages. Tesseract doesn't have a built-in GUI, but there are several available from the 3rdParty page. Tesseract is compatible with many programming languages and frameworks through wrappers that can be found here. It can be used with the existing layout analysis to recognize text within a large document, or it can be used in conjunction with an external text detector to recognize text from an image of a single text line as shown in figure 4. [11]

Figure 4: OCR Process Flow

Tesseract 4.00 includes a new neural network subsystem configured as a text line recognizer. It has its origins in origins in OCRopus' Python-based LSTM implementation but has been redesigned for Tesseract in C++. The neural network system in Tesseract pre-dates TensorFlow but is compatible with it, as there is a network description language called Variable Graph Specification Language (VGSL), that is also available for TensorFlow.

To recognize an image containing a single character, we typically use a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). Text of arbitrary length is a sequence of characters, and such problems are solved using RNNs and LSTM is a popular form of RNN.

How Tesseract OCR Model works: LSTMs are great at learning sequences but slow down a lot when the number of states is too large. There are empirical results that suggest it is better to ask an LSTM to learn a long sequence than a short sequence of many classes. Tesseract developed from OCRopus model in Python, which was a fork of a LSMT in C++, called CLSTM. CLSTM is an implementation of the LSTM recurrent neural network model in C++, using the Eigen library for numerical computations, as represented in figure 5. [12]

Figure 5: How Tesseract OCR Model Work

Legacy Tesseract 3.x was dependent on the multi-stage process where we can differentiate steps:

- Word finding.
- Line finding.
- Character classification.

Word finding was done by organizing text lines into blobs, and the lines and regions are analyzed for fixed pitch or proportional text. Text lines are broken into words differently according to the kind of character spacing. Recognition then proceeds as a two-pass process. In the first pass, an attempt is made to recognize each word in turn. Each word that is satisfactory is passed to an adaptive classifier as training data. The adaptive classifier then gets a chance to recognize text lower more accurately down the page.

Modernization of the Tesseract tool was an effort on code cleaning and adding a new LSTM model. The input image is processed in boxes (rectangle) line by line feeding into the LSTM model and giving output. In the image below we can visualize how it works.

After testing our model, we notice that the accuracy is not perfect enough, as there may be some noise in the images, and some handwriting was not clear, and our goal is to reach the highest possible accuracy, so we want the highest possible ability in reading texts, even if the image has noise or writing Bad, that's why we used Google Cloud Vision API like object detection. [13]

3.3-Feature3: Describe Scene (Image to text):

Describe Scene or in other words “image Caption” is the process of generating textual description of an image, which makes the blind person imagine the appearance in front of him, it uses both Natural Language Processing and Computer Vision to generate the captions. [14]

In this feature, we will implement a caption generator by using CNN (Convolutional Neural Networks) and LSTM (Long Term Memory). The image features will be extracted from Exception which is a CNN model trained on the ImageNet dataset and then we input the features into the LSTM model which will be responsible for generating comments on the image.

Encoder: The Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) can be thought of as an encoder. The input image is given to CNN to extract the features. The last hidden state of the CNN is connected to the Decoder as shown in figure 6.

Figure 6: Feature Extraction

Flicker Dataset: The Flickr30k dataset is a popular benchmark for sentence-based picture portrayal. The dataset is comprised of 31,783 images that capture people engaged in everyday activities and events. Each image has a descriptive caption (5 captions). Flickr30k is used for understanding the visual media (image) that correspond to a linguistic expression (description of the image). This dataset is commonly used as a standard benchmark for sentence-based image description.

Decoder: The Decoder is a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) which does language modelling up to the word level. The first-time step receives the encoded output from the encoder and the <START> vector, as represented in table 2. [15]

Table 2: Caption Generator

x1(feature vector)	x2(Text sequence)	y (word to predict)
feature	start,	two
feature	start, two	dogs
feature	start, two, dogs	drink
feature	start, two, dogs, drink	water
feature	start, two, dogs, drink, water	end

LSTM: is a type of RNN (recurrent neural network), LSTM (Long short-term memory) can work

with sequence prediction problems. It is mostly used for the next word prediction purposes, as in Google search our system shows the next word based on the previous text. Throughout the processing of inputs, LSTM is used to carry out the relevant information and to discard non-relevant information as shown in figure 7. [16]

Figure 7: Caption Generator

So, to summarize that, we can say that Image Caption is divided into 3 stages: Extract Features from image: CNN, get sequence generator: RNN and finally merge CNN and RNN together to train the model.

3.4-Feature 4: Cash and Food Recognition (Image Classification):

Image classification is a computer vision task of assigning a label to an image. The label can be a category, such as "cat" or "dog," or it can be a more specific object, such as "Siamese cat" or "Golden Retriever." Image classification is a challenging task because images can be very complex and contain many different objects.

In our case we use image classification to classify food and cash, we use CNN architecture s image classification problem where we consider each category in the cash as class.

Image Classification attempts to connect an image to a set of class labels. It is a supervised learning problem, wherein a set of pre-labeled training data is fed to a machine learning algorithm. This algorithm attempts to learn the visual features contained in the training images associated with each label and classify unlabeled images accordingly, Image classification involves the extraction of features from the image to observe some patterns in the dataset as shown in figure 8. [17]

Figure 8: CNN for Image Classification

Transfer learning: is a machine learning method where a model developed for a task is reused as the starting point for a model on a second task. It is a popular approach in deep learning where pre-trained models are used as the starting point on the model. A pre-trained model refers to a model or a saved network created by someone else and trained on a large dataset to solve a similar problem. AI teams can use a pretrained model as a starting point, instead of building a model from scratch. Examples of successful large-scale pre-trained language models are Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) and the Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT-n), as represented in figure 9. [18]

Figure 9: Transfer Learning

Model Architecture: In this problem several models have been applied to the dataset like (VGG16, ResNet50, alexnet), but we use mobilenet model it gives us good accuracy and at the same time it gives a low FLOPS (is a measure of computer performance), as shown in figure 10.

Figure 10: Accuracy VS MADDs VS model

Select optimizer, loss function, learning rate: After trying many values on many models, Research, we found that the following values give the high accuracy in this model.

1. Optimizer: stochastic gradient descent (It is easier to fit into memory due to a single training sample being processed by the network (It is computationally fast as only one sample is processed at a time)).
2. Learning rate =0.001
3. Criterion: crossentropyloss (this is particularly useful when you have an unbalanced training set).

3.5-Feature 5: Face Recognition:

Face recognition is a method of recognizing an individual using their face. Face recognition systems can be used to identify individuals in photos, videos, or in real-time. The main motivation behind building a real-time face recognition system is to enable faster processing and seamless integration in various real-world applications such as public safety systems, authentication systems, retail-store systems, etc. This feature is divided into two things (Detection then Recognition), first detect the faces in the photo and get the boundary of each face in the image then recognize each face by comparing this face with images that stored in our dataset, as represented on figure 11. [19]

Figure 11: Face Recognition

There are two main approaches to face detection:

- 1- Feature-based face detection: Feature-based face detection algorithms identify faces by looking for specific facial features, such as the eyes, nose, and mouth. These algorithms can be very accurate, but they can be slow and computationally expensive.
- 2- Appearance-based face detection: Appearance-based face detection algorithms identify faces by looking for patterns in the image that are characteristic of faces. These algorithms can be faster and less computationally expensive than feature-based algorithms, but they can be less accurate.

Most modern face detection algorithms use a combination of feature-based and appearance-based approaches.

After detecting the faces in image then we need to know the name of this person, and this is the role of face recognition.

To make face recognition work, we need to have a dataset of photos also composed of several images per character and comparison photo. For example, in our example, we have a dataset folder (images) that has folders of each person in our team that contain several photos for him.

With the usual OpenCV procedure, we extract the image and convert it into RGB color format. Then we do the “face encoding” that encode the face into pixels and then compare this pixel with the pixels of image we need to detect and knowing the managers of the convergence of pixels between them. [20]

4-Proposed System and Implementation

4.1- Proposed System:

Figure 12: Proposed System

The system is divided into two main parts, the first is the phone, which through an application represents a control device for the entire system, the second part of the system is the minicomputer, which operates through all the features in the system.

The system starts by requesting the user to run a specific feature, by touching the button for the feature in the application on the phone, and the phone emits a sound to confirm to the user that this is the feature he wants, then sends it to the small computer to implement it, so the computer asks the glasses that have a camera installed to take a picture. It takes it, processes it, runs the form that implements this image, then sends the output from the form in the form of text, which it sends to the application to convert it into sound, then it outputs the output to the user in the form of sound as represented in figure 12.

4.2-Implementation:

Our proposed system utilizes various tools, libraries, and hardware components to accomplish its objectives. We employ several popular computer vision frameworks such as PyTorch, TensorFlow, and OpenCV to train our models. Additionally, we utilize Google Cloud API to improve the accuracy of our object detection and text reader capabilities.

All these operations are processed on a Raspberry Pi minicomputer, a highly versatile and cost-effective computer that can be used in a wide range of projects. We connect a mini camera to the Raspberry Pi to capture images, which are then analyzed and processed accordingly.

To facilitate user control of the glasses, we have developed a simple mobile app using the Flutter framework. The app allows blind users to select the desired feature, which is then executed on the Raspberry Pi.

In the mobile app, we have incorporated several libraries, including TTS for converting the output from the Raspberry Pi to audio for the user to hear. Additionally, we use Google Translate API to provide output in multiple languages.

Finally, we use the Python Socket library to connect the mobile app with the Raspberry Pi and facilitate communication between the two devices.

Conclusion

Computer vision technology helps the blind and visually impaired in their daily lives without needing for the help of other people through an intelligent system. The proposed system includes various features such as object detection, reading text, describe scene, face recognition, cash recognition, and food recognition. This proposed system is controlled through a mobile application that has been specifically designed for the blind and can be operated using voice commands.

What sets this system apart from others is its unique features such as food recognition, face recognition, and cash recognition. With these capabilities, blind and visually impaired individuals can independently identify different types of food, recognize people's faces, and identify different denominations of currency, which would otherwise require assistance from others.

The proposed system is composed of a mini-camera and mini-computer, which work in conjunction with the mobile application to provide a user-friendly experience for the visually impaired. The proposed system offers a comprehensive and integrated solution that aims to improve the quality of life for blind and visually impaired individuals by reducing their reliance on other people.

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